

FABRICATION OF ES-NANOFIBER IMPRINTING PLASTIC MOLD AND MICRO-STRUCTURED PARTS BY NANPOWDER PRINTING

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to develop the eco-friendly fabrication method for micro-structured parts with high aspect ratio. To achieve this purpose, nanopowder printing (nPP) process was adopted to the plastic mold with microscopic textures prepared by electrospinning nanofiber imprinting (ES-NFI) method. The novel method named as ES-NFI sacrificial plastic mold nanopowder printing (ES-NFI/nPP) was proposed and demonstrated in this study. ES-NFI method was applied to Si form that have several patterns including line-space, multi pillars and multi holes with various micro-structured sizes, thus plastic molds with finer microscopic textures were prepared for nPP process. The nanofiber was produced by electro-spinning (ES) process which provides a simple and versatile method for generating ultrathin fibers using variety of materials. The ES condition on the diameter of nanofiber was optimized to generate ultrafine fiber steady. By melting ES-nanofiber coated on Si forms, the plastic molds with the microscopic textures were replicated properly by polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) polymer. The effect of aspect ratio in microstructures on the shape transcription was investigated by changing the size of microscopic texture of Si form from 1 μ m to 50 μ m wide for 10 μ m high. The experimental result shown that the microstructures with 1 μ m wide to 10 μ m high could be formed precisely on the surface of plastic mold after melting ES-nanofiber with approx. 100nm in mean diameter. Then it was confirmed that the ES-NFI method proposed in this study was superior for fabricating the plastic mold with finer microstructures and it was preferable in comparing with a conventional dipping method. This conclusion does not only attribute a good transcription to finer fiber, but it is considered to be obtained by in-situ extraction of solvent during ES process. Also the composition of paste materials made from TiO₂ nano-sized powder and PEG water-soluble binder was varied for the optimization. It was shown from the experimental results that the sintered parts with microstructures of 50 μ m wide for 10 μ m high could be formed soundly, and it was also desirable to use the paste materials with lower content of binding polymer in keeping adequate viscosity. It was concluded that ES-NFI/nPP method was a useful method for fabricating the micro-structured parts in the mass production.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is a variety of manufacturing methods for the micro-structured parts such as micro-machining using micro-tool, laser, electro-beam, and micro-etching, micro-imprinting, electroplating, micro-deposition, micro-molding and screen printing using photolithography, and so on [1]. However most of these methods have significant limitations on applicable materials, sizes and facilities. On the other hand, powder sintering is one of useful processes having great advantages on materials, productivity, shape and facility cost. Recently it is well known that powder injection molding (PIM), which encompasses metal powder injection molding (MIM) and ceramic powder injection molding (CIM) is a net-shape process for the manufacturing of high volume and high precision components for use in a variety of industries. The micro-miniaturization of dimension and structures in PIM is facing with various technical problems, such as incomplete filling to narrow cavity, failure in demolding of fragile green compacts, and deformation in debinding and sintering process. Therefore micro-PIM (μ -PIM) process is a more sophisticated process for tiny metal components and micro-structured parts [2]. As further micro-miniaturization of μ -PIM parts develops, the application areas are hoping to expand

from just compaction of mechanical components to micro integrated devices such as micro reactor, micro mixer, micro actuator and micro sensor which have being manufactured by micro system technology or micro-electro-mechanical systems (MEMS) technology [1]. These fabrication methods are based on semi-conductor process, thus the applicable material is mainly silicon, gallium arsenide or also limited to metals which can be deposited by electroplating, evaporation and sputtering. In addition, as for polymer, resist film formed by etching on silicon wafer or plastic patterns replicated by stamper of nano-imprint lithography (NIL) is available.

The μ -MIM process is very useful for the manufacturing of micro-sized and micro-structured metallic parts, but it is facing with various technical problems in each process. For example, it is difficult to fill feedstock completely into a narrow cavity and to demold fragile green compacts from a metallic mold in injection molding process. A careful handling is also required in the debinding and sintering processes. There are many other technical problems such as measuring of the density, the shape and mechanical properties of sintered parts. The solutions for filling of viscous feedstock into the fine mold and fabricating of fine mold are shown in addition to the effectiveness and the disadvantages. The use of finer powder is essential to fill the feedstock into several tenth and a few micron-sized cavity. However, nano-sized powder has extremely high specific surface area, thus the tap density is very low and the viscosity of the feedstock increases remarkably. It is also susceptible to oxidation and relatively high production cost. Therefore these properties result in adverse effect for the production and the utilization. The fluidity of the feedstock is improved generally by increasing the binder content, but it makes lower the quality and the mechanical property of the sintered parts because the density of green compact become lower and the remaining carbon content increases. On the other hand, it is not easy to fabricate precisely a metallic mold, but a plastic is more superior for processability of the fine mold. In addition, a plastic mold is much superior for filling of the feedstock because its low thermal conductivity which delays solidification of melted materials. Moreover it is not necessary to demold a green compact from a plastic mold which can be decomposed thermally in debinding process. As a result, if there is a solution to the problem in sintering and injection of finer metal powder into plastic mold, a sintered part with smooth surface and good transcription can expect to be manufactured by MIM process. Therefore the trade-off problem needs to be solved by any innovative technologies.

For the above reasons, authors have developed the sacrificial plastic mold (SP-mold) insert μ -MIM process. The innovative process was named as μ -SPiMIM which is basically divided into three steps; 1) manufacturing of SP-mold, 2) injection molding of MIM feedstock into SP-mold insert, and demolding the green compact and SP-mold insert part as one component, handling to the debinding-sintering process, and finally 3) debinding to eliminate the SP-mold and polymeric binder followed by sintering process. Therefore, the μ -SPiMIM process has great potentials to improve the filling, demolding and handling, and to produce the tiny parts with 3 dimensional complex shapes and fine structures. The SP-molds used in this process can be manufactured by several types of methods such as injection molding, machining, rapid-prototyping, hot-embossing and lithography and so on [2].

In this study, a further novel process was proposed to overcome the disadvantages in injection molding process and also to achieve the full shape transcription from SP-mold with higher aspect ratio microstructures. This process can contribute to the mass production for a large area device with consideration to be lower facility cost and environmental load.

2 NOVEL FABRICATION METHOD PROPOSED FOR MICRO-STRUCTURED PARTS

The processability of a variety of μ -SPiMIM processes authors have already studied is summarized in Figure 1 in compared with the other precision processing and machining methods. A conventional rapid plot typing is difficult to manufacture SP-mold with micro-scale structure and high dimensional accuracy. Then RP/ μ -SPiMIM method is not superior compared to micro machining such as micro-cutting, micro-EDM and micro-casting on the size of products, but it has a great potential to manufacture complex shaped parts. Further micro-miniaturization and surface quality improvement of rapid plot typing are required for μ -SPiMIM process, micro rapid plot-typing using stereo-lithography and 3D-printing technology is a prospective method for manufacturing of fine structured SP-mold. On the other hand, LIGA/ μ -SPiMIM and Resist/ μ -SPiMIM are very hopeful combined methods for

manufacturing the metallic micro-structured parts with high aspect ratio. The size possible for manufacturing is ranged from hundreds micrometers to tens micrometers. The problems are included high manufacturing cost and shape limitation of SP-mold. Furthermore, NIL techniques has a possibility for manufacturing a single digit micrometer-sized structured part, but technical problems on the quality of sintered parts using nano-scale metal powders should be cleared in NIL/ μ -SPiMIM process. In addition, evaluation methods and designing of micro devices are hoped with effectiveness of these micro-structure and a variety of metallic own properties. These μ -SPiMIM processes have a unique advantage on fabricating as a one component with macro-scale and micro-scale structures made from a variety of materials. Also the micro-scale open and closed porous structures can be formed in sintering parts. This is not accomplished by semiconductor processes and depositions methods. Therefore it is hoping to use advanced applications such as micro reactor and micro-patterned electrodes with catalyst activity for fuel cell and battery manufacturing or micro-sensors for medical devices.

The target of this study is to develop the eco-friendly alternative process for manufacturing the metallic or ceramic sheet-like micro-structured parts with single digit micrometers in width to 10 μ m in height as pointed out in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Processability of a variety of μ -SPiMIM processes and target of this study.

To accomplish the target of this study, the fabrication of SP-mold by micro-imprinting method using electrospinning nanofiber which was named as ES-NFI method was proposed. Additionally, the compaction method of powder into SP-mold was chosen contact printing using nanopowder paste which is named as nPP method instead of injection molding. This combination of ES/NFI and nPP methods was applied in this study. The flow of ES-NFI/nPP process is shown in Figure 2. In ES-NFI process as shown in Figure 2 (1), nanofiber was spun electrically on Si form from liquid solution of polymer. The ES-nanofiber was melt on Si form in hot air dryer. The ES-nanofiber film is very thin and weak, then was reinforced with coating and melting liquid solution. After this operation, SP-mold was obtained by demolding the film from Si form. Subsequently the nPP process is proceeded as shown in Figure 2 (2). Paste consisting of nanopowder and water soluble binder was prepared adequately and was filled into SP-mold by contact printing. The green compact was heated with SP-mold as one component to remove the water containing into the green compacts as shown in Figure 2 (3). Finally the SP-mold and polymeric binder was removed in the furnace and followed by sintering as shown in Figure 2 (4). Sintering part with microstructures was obtained in large quantities at one time via these processes.

Figure 2: Flow of ES-NFI/nPP process.

3 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

This chapter describes the experimental materials used for ES-NFI and contact printing, and also these methods and conditions. These materials and conditions were one example for trial production, and then the ES-NFI/nPP method proposed in this study can be broadly-applicable for a variety of materials and fabrication conditions.

3.1 Electrospinning nanofiber process

Electrospinning method is suited to produce nanofibers from polymer dissolved into solvent. It provides a simple and versatile method for generating ultrathin fibers using variety of materials. This method uses an electrical charge to draw very fine fibers from a liquid [3, 4]. The diameter of the fibers is typically on the submicron scale, and it is typically effected by several experimental parameters such as, applied voltage, feed rate and resin concentration. Figure 3 shows the SEM image of ES-nanofiber fabricated at an optimized fabrication condition as listed in Table 1. Liquid solution used for electrospinning is PMMA (Polymethylmethacrylate) polymer dissolved by DMF (N,N-dimethylmethanamide) and CHCl_3 (Chloroform). The concentration of liquid solution was 17mass% and spinning time was 1.8ks in commercial ES-nanofiber machine (MECC Co., Ltd., NANON-01A).

Figure 2: SEM image of ES-nanofiber fabricated at Table 1

Table 1: Optimized fabrication condition for ES-nanofiber.

Applied voltage, V_i (kV)	30
Feed rate, F_d (ml/h)	0.2
Resin concentration, C_s (mass%)	17

3.2 Si form for ES-nanofiber imprinting

Figure 3 shows the dimensions of Si form used for ES-nanofiber imprinting. The Si form was manufactured by photo-lithography etching process, and has three types of microstructure patterns; (a) Line-space pattern, (b) Multi pillar pattern and (c) Multi hole pattern. The sizes of these patterns were varied from $w=1$ to $50\mu\text{m}$ in width to $h=10\mu\text{m}$ in height. The aspect ratio of height to width (h/w) is from 0.2 to 10. The surface of Si form was treated by coating for demolding, and was cleaned with organic solvent in each operation.

Figure 3: Dimensions of Si form with various patterns used for ES-nanofiber imprinting.

3.3 Materials used for contact printing

The materials used for contact printing in nPP process is paste which was mixed nanoscale TiO_2 particle (Reagent, CAS.NO 1317-80-2) as shown in Figure 4 and polyethylene glycol (PEG, molecular weight:20,000, Regent, CAS.NO 25322-68-3) dissolved in water. These materials were mixed at room temperature with planetary centrifugal mixer (THINKY Co., Ltd, AR-100). The viscosities of the pastes mixed at various H_2O contents in constant 40mass% of solid loading were shown in Figure 5. The viscosity of paste is dependent significantly on H_2O contents. Lower viscosity of part is easier to

Figure 4: SEM image of TiO_2 particle used.

Figure 5: Viscosity of pastes with various H_2O contents.

fill in narrow cavity of SP-mold, but it is poor shape-retaining and lower density after sintering. Therefore, composition ratio of paste such as solid loading, fraction of polymer binder and H₂O content should be optimized in considering the both moldability and densification. In this study, two types of composition of pastes were prepared as shown in Table 2, and the effect of solid loading and viscosity on the microstructure of green compact or sintered parts was investigated.

Table 2: Composition ratio and viscosity of pastes used for contact printing.

Solid loading	TiO ₂	PEG	H ₂ O	Viscosity
40mass%	12.9mass%	19.4mass%	67.7mass%	1270cP
	13.3mass%	20.0mass%	66.7mass%	1746cP
	13.8mass%	20.7mass%	65.5mass%	1905cP
56mass%	14.7mass%	11. mass%	73.5mass%	1746cP

3.4 Contact printing, sintering and evaluation method

The appearance of contact printing process is illustrated in Figure 5. Desk-size screen printing machine (Neotechno Japan Co., Ltd., NJ-15PHP) was modified to meet the specification of contact printing. Paste consisting of TiO₂ nanopowder was printed on ES-NFI mold using a squeegee. The green compact and ES-NFI mold as one component was demolded from Al frame, and was put on the Al₂O₃ setter plate. It was debinded at 300°C for 1.8ks and was sintered at 500°C for 1.8ks using electric muffle furnace (Yamadadenki Co., LTd., YF-120-PS).

The surface of green compacts and sintered parts were observed with SEM (Hitachi high technology Co., Ltd., SU1510) and the cross-sectional profiles were measured with laser microscope (Olympus Co., Ltd., OLS4100).

Figure 5: Appearance of contact printing process.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Shape transcription of ES-NFI molds fabricated using Si form with various sizes and patterns of microscopic textures was evaluated by comparing with Si form. Also the shape retention of green compacts obtained by contact printing into those ES-NFI molds was evaluated by SEM images and laser microscopic profile measurement. Moreover shape retention and shrinkage state of the sintered parts manufactured from those green compacts were focused by contrast with shape of ES-NFI molds and green compacts.

4.1 ES-Nanofiber imprinted mold

SEM images of Si form and plastic molds produced using Si form with $w=1\mu\text{m}$ and $5\mu\text{m}$ microscopic textures by ES-NFI process are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively. As shown in Figure 6 where Si form has microstructures of $w=1\mu\text{m}$, surface micro-asperities are transcribed into ES-NFI mold fully and accurately for (a) line-space pattern and (b) multi pillar pattern, but have an absence of pillars partly for (c) multi hole pattern. This is assumed to be due to the resistance of air trap to fill resin into hole of Si form or insufficient strength of pillar to stand on itself. On the other hand, as shown in Figure 7 where Si form has microstructures of $w=5\mu\text{m}$, ES-NFI molds are transcribed fully and accurately for any patterns. From these experimental results, it is confirmed that ES-NFI process proposed in this study is superior for fabricating the plastic mold with finer microstructures. This conclusion does not only attribute a good transcription to finer fiber, but it is considered to be obtained by in-situ extraction of solvent during ES process.

Figure 6: SEM images of Si form and sacrificial plastic molds produced by ES-NFI process ($w=1\mu\text{m}$)

Figure 7: SEM images of Si form and sacrificial plastic molds produced by ES-NFI process ($w=5\mu\text{m}$)

4.2 Green compacts and sintered parts

SEM images of green compacts and sintered parts produced using ES-NFI mold with $w=1\mu\text{m}$ and $5\mu\text{m}$ microscopic textures are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, respectively. As shown in Figure 8 where Si form has microstructures of $w=1\mu\text{m}$, line and space holds in green compact, and these make contacts by sintering shrinkage for (a) line-space pattern. However surface micro-asperities are not visible fully but obvious cracks occurs for (b) multi pillar pattern and (c) multi hole pattern. This is supposed that submicron powder paste is very hard to fill into such a single digit micron-sized hole and pillar. On the other hand, as shown in Figure 9 where Si form has microstructures of $w=5\mu\text{m}$, line and space, multi hole are formed obviously in green compacts for (a) line-space pattern and (c) multi hole pattern, then these sintered parts hold wholly the shape formation with some defects. However the filling of paste is insufficient in the green compact for (b) multi pillar pattern. The result suggests that it is hard to fill the submicron powder paste into a single digit micron-sized hole of ES-NFI mold.

Figure 8: SEM images of green compacts and sintered parts ($w=1\mu\text{m}$)

Figure 9: SEM images of green compacts and sintered parts ($w=5\mu\text{m}$)

Figure 10 shows the profile curves of a representative unit of ES-NFI mold (Line-space pattern, $w=10\mu\text{m}$) and green compacts fabricated using pastes with various viscosities. When high viscous paste with $\eta=1905\text{cP}$ was used, paste could not filled deeply into the bottom of ES-NFI mold. While low viscous paste with $\eta=1270\text{cP}$ was used, paste contained much H_2O , the shape transcription is inferior at the top edge of line pattern after drying. It was therefore found that intermediate viscous paste with $\eta=1746\text{cP}$ was preferable for shape transcription to ES-NFI mold.

Figure 11 shows the profile curves of a representative unit of sintered parts fabricated by printing pastes with varied solid loadings into ES-NFI mold (Line-space pattern, $w=10\mu\text{m}$). When paste with 56mass% solid loading was used, sharp corners are visible comparatively at the top edges of line pattern. In contrast, when paste with 40mass% solid loading was used, rounded corners was formed. As an experimental results, it is concluded that a higher fraction of nanopowder containing paste is more preferable in shape transcription as long as the viscosity of paste can fill fully into micro-channels.

Figure 10: Profile curves of a representative unit of ES-NFI mold and green compacts fabricated using pastes with various viscosities (Line-space pattern, $w=10\mu\text{m}$).

Figure 11: Profile curves of a representative unit of sintered parts fabricated using pastes with varied solid loadings (Line-space pattern, $w=10\mu\text{m}$).

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the electrospinning nanofiber imprinting (ES-NFI) method was developed to produce plastic sheet with a single digit microstructures. This was applied to the mold for contact printing using paste consisting of nanopowder, and followed by debinding and sintering processes. The ES-NFI sacrificial plastic mold nanopowder printing (ES-NFI/nPP) process was demonstrated to fabricate TiO₂ micro-structured parts. ES-NFI mold was prepared using Si form that have three types of microstructures including line-space, multi pillars and multi holes. As a result, the plastic molds with fine microscopic textures were replicated properly by polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) polymer. The size of microstructure is accomplished to 1μm wide for 10μm high. It was concluded that ES-NFI method was superior for fabricating the plastic mold with finer microstructures. Also the composition of paste materials made from TiO₂ nano-sized powder and PEG water-soluble binder was varied for the optimization. It was shown from the experimental results that the sintered part with microstructures of 50μm wide for 10μm high could be formed soundly, and it was also desirable to use the paste materials with lower content of binder polymer in keeping adequate viscosity. It was confirmed that ES-NFI/nPP method was a useful method for fabricating the single-digit micrometer structured parts in the mass production.

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